

Buying perception and brand awareness of the rural consumer towards branded products

1. Firozkhan Pathan

PhD Scholar

Department of MBA, Centre for P.G. Studies

Visvesvaraya Technological University Belagavi

2. Dr. S M Porapur

Assistant Professor

Department of MBA, Centre for P.G. Studies

Visvesvaraya Technological University Belagavi

ABSTRACT: Today, talking to rural consumers reveal that their thoughts and ideas are similar to that of urban consumers and Rural is often restricted now to a physical space or geography. Most villages have pakka roads, electrification and proper housing. But crucially, what is important for marketers is that there is a change in the mindset of rural consumers. The per capita consumption in India is much lower than the per capita consumption in other developing markets and one of the reasons for that is that rural consumption, rural penetration and rural frequency are much lower than in the urban segment. However, it is important to look beyond the obvious and understand that a lot of rural income is disposable, so the ability to consume and the willingness to consume are constantly evolving. And that's why rural India represents an enormous opportunity.

KEYWORDS: Buying Perception, Brand Awareness & Rural Consumer Preferences

1. INTRODUCTION

Rural markets are an important and growing market. The rural market in India is not separate entity in itself and it is highly influenced by the sociological and behavioral factors operating in the country. Rural markets offer vast growth opportunities like untapped market, large population, and huge scope for penetration. At the same time this market faces some challenges as well urban market is almost reaching towards the saturation point, thus there is an urgent need to focus on rural development. Moreover, more than 70% of India's population lives in villages and constitutes a big market for industry. FMCG and Consumer durable goods is closest companion Retail sector, both are likely to create most of the jobs in India in the coming years primarily in functions like marketing, sales, advertising, supply chain, logistics, human resources, product packaging and development, finance, operations, general management, supervising and so on.

Brands and Branded products that are sold in urban quickly and at relatively high cost. There are some brands that are sold in Rural such as day-to-day household needs other than grocery,

ranging from packaged foodstuff, dairy products, cooking oil, bread, butter, cereals, beverages like tea & coffee, pharmaceuticals, confectionery, biscuits, glassware, stationary items, watches, toiletries, detergents, shampoos, skin care products, cosmetics, toothpaste, dish washing liquid, shaving cream, razor, batteries, shoe polish, energy drinks, soft drinks, clothing, furniture and household accessories to electronic goods like cell phones, laptops, computers, digital cameras etc.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH PAPER

The objective of the study was to understand the buying perception and brand awareness of the rural consumer towards Branded Products. For this, the objectives of the Research Work are as under

- ❖ To study the perception of the rural consumer towards branded products.
- ❖ To examine the brand preference and awareness of rural consumer towards branded products.
- ❖ To study the impact of media on brand awareness & Preferences.
- ❖ To identify brands awareness and branding awareness in rural areas
- ❖ To check potential market for brands in rural areas

3. STATEMENTS OF THE PROBLEMS

There is a problem in Brand availability, Brand Awareness and brands Preferences. Despite of many promotions on Print and TV Media by companies and Govt Authority. This problem has negatively affected Brands and theirs Brands Equity because of Low income and Literacy. A possible cause of this problem is High Cost of the Branded Products and ignorance of Rural Areas. Perhaps a study which investigates Branding Awareness and Brands Preferences by a Research Methods Statistical Factoring and Regression could help resolve the situation.

- ❖ Lack of Brand Awareness
- ❖ Low income Level
- ❖ Lack of Brands preferences
- ❖ Lack of brands availability
- ❖ Low Literacy level
- ❖

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

The methodology of the study is based on the primary as well as secondary data. The study depended mainly on the primary data collected through a well-framed and structured questionnaire to elicit the well- considered opinions of the respondents. The study was confined to 5 villages of the Ramdurg district Belgaum Karnataka State a rural oriented region and about 115 are villages. 5

villages of 1 Ramdurg taluk were chosen for survey. In all 50 respondents were considered as sample size from different age groups who were classified on the basis of their responses with the help of questionnaire & discussions.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Interpretation and Analysis of the Data are as follows below

Table: 5.1 Brands Recognizes in the rural Area

SI No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Brand Knows	26	52
2	Brand Don't Knows	24	48
3	Total	50	100

Table No 1 Shows nearly in the ratio 50:50; 52% respondents knows what does mean Brands and branded products whereas 48% of the respondents does not knows what does brand means , this shows how rural people recognize the brands positively and its show there is huge potential for brands in Rural Area

Table: 5.2 Preference towards brands in terms of Quality, Prices & Prestige

SI No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Prefer Branded always yes	0	0
2	Never	48	96
3	Only when Quality Important	2	4
4	Rarely	0	0
5	Total	50	100

Table 2: With the huge deference Margin 96% respondents does not prefer the Brands only 4% of the respondent feel it's require when quality is necessary.

Table: 5.3 Rural People's buying store formats

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Departmental Stores	8	16
2	Super market	2	4
3	Convenient	0	0
4	Kirana store	40	80
5	Total	50	100

Table 3: In the above table it shows 80% of Rural People usually buys in kirana Stores and 16% merely buy in Departmental stores & 2 % Super market.

Table: 5.4 Respondents consulting influencer before buying the Brands

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Education Person	2	4
2	Shop Keeper	2	4
3	Siblings	8	16
4	Friends	36	72
5	Total	50	100

Table 4: While buying Brands 72% of respondents consults firstly to their friends whereas 16% to their Siblings & 4% to the Educated and Shop keeper respectively

Table: 5.5 Preference of Generic Products for easy availability

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Yes	48	96
2	No	2	4
3	Mostly	0	0
4	Total	50	100

Table 5: Shows 96% of the respondents says yes for preferring the Generic products because of the easy and more available, 4% says No & Zero for Mostly.

Table: 5.6 Brands are Costlier and expensive

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Yes	48	96
2	No	2	4
3	Total	50	100

Table 6: The above table shows that 96% of the respondents says brands are costlier and 4% says No

Table: 5.7 Rural People how Loyal to the Braded Products

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Yes	2	4
2	No	48	96
3	Up to Certain Limit	0	0
4	Other Reason	0	0
5	Total	50	100

Table 7: Rural people are less loyal to the branded products because 96% of the respondent says it only 4% says they are Loyal.

Table: 5.8 Aspects makes rural people to buy branded products

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Quality	48	96
2	Communication prices	0	0
3	Free trail	0	0
4	value for money if other	2	4
5	Total	50	100

Table 8: Shows that 96% of the respondent buys the branded products because of the quality and 4% for value for money sake and the rest lays Zero, Price communication & Free Trails.

Table: 5.9 Brands awareness and its promotion in Rural Area

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Hoarding	4	8
2	In shop branding	2	4
3	TV Ads	24	48
4	Friends and followers	20	40
5	Total	50	100

Table 9: TV Advertising gave 48% of the publicity in the rural area and 40% rural consumers aware the Brands by friends and followers, 8% by Hoardings and least in 4% by In shop Brandings

Table: 5.10 Apart from direct benefits rural consumers what else looks for in the Brands

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Image of the product	34	68
2	Identification from other user of the brand	10	20
3	Prestige	0	0
4	Fashion	6	12
5	Total	50	100

Table 10: Shows that the 68% of the rural consumers looks apart from the direct benefits is Image of the Products, 16% Identification from other user of the brand, 12% Prestige and Zero % fashion

Table: 5.11 Demographical statuses

Sl No	Respondents	Frequency	%
1	Monthly Income between 3-10 Thousand	35	70
2	Monthly Income between 10-20 Thousand	12	24
3	Monthly Income between 20-40 Thousand	03	06
4	Total	50	100

Figure: 1

What Does Brand Means

Figure: 2

In which store format preference to buy

Figure: 3 Media preference

Figure: 4

Brand Perception

FINDINGS

Results of the study have been concluded in the following section. The average brand awareness of the respondents in the rural market is they knew the brands 54%, people identify the brands 70% and people do not prefer the brands are 95%, this shows that people in the rural areas have a slightly above average awareness about most of the products available in the market. In case of prices consciousness, respondents have given the Brands are high costs. In case of Brand Awareness people aware the brands on TV 50%, by Hoardings 8%, by referral of friends 38% and in shop Branding 4%. As far as the sources from which the respondents became aware, the 1st rank goes to Television, 2nd to friends, 3rd to Hoardings and 4th to In Shop Brandings. It is clear from the above study that respondents of different gender groups have different attitude towards the various brand products. Income factor greatly influences the demand for branded products, as is clear from the study; the dependents are more aware and conscious about the brand of their daily consumption goods.

CONCLUSION

The brand awareness in rural areas particularly in respect of beauty care and health care products is showing an increasing tendency. (Most of the people both from illiterate & literate groups prefer branded products with the belief that quality is assured as the manufacturers are reputed companies but income constraint them to buy and most of them buy FMCG in Kirana Stores)

There is an increasing trend among the people of rural areas about the awareness of various brands of the daily consumption goods. People of rural areas are becoming more conscious about their health and other aspects of life.

This change in the attitude to spend more on the highly priced branded products among high income groups in rural areas clearly suggests that there is an ample scope for such products to capture the markets in these areas by increasing the supply of these products. Usage of branded products is seen as status elevator in the villages. The need of the hour is only to make aware the rural customers regarding the brand availability of daily consumption goods by educating them about the need to the use of branded products.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.R.Kothari, Research Methodology. New Age International Publishers (2004)
- [2] M.M.Munshi & K.Gayathri, Research Methods, Himalaya Publications(2017)
- [3] T.P.Gupalaswamy, 2nd Edition, Rural Marketing Environment, Problem & Strategies, Vikas Publishing House Pvt Ltd (2005)
- [4] K.S. Habeeb-Ur-Raheman, Rural Marketing in India, Himalaya Publishing House (2011)
- [5] J.K. Sharma, Business Statistic, Problems & Solutions, Donling Kindersley (India) Pvt Ltd, Licensees of Pearson Education in South Asia (2010)
- [6] Dr O.R. Krishnaswami & Dr M. Ranganathan, Methods of Research in Social Science, Himalaya Publishing House (2016)